

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Niobium[†]

B. KESHAVAN* and K. P. KRISHNA PRASAD

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Mysore-570 006

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Due to the technical importance, a wide variety of methods have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of niobium¹. However, the number of chromogenic reagents which are available, are relatively small for the determination of niobium in the presence of associated metal ions like tantalum, iron and manganese. During the course of our investigations on the analytical applications of phenothiazines², it was observed that methotrimeprazine (MTM) forms a mixed-ligand complex with niobium in hydrochloric acid medium in the presence of thiocyanate. The present communication describes a spectrophotometric method for the determination of niobium based on the above observation.

Results and Discussion

Niobium(v) forms an yellow coloured mixed-ligand complex with thiocyanate and MTM at room temperature in hydrochloric acid medium which could be completely extracted into trichloroethylene. It has been observed that promethazine hydrochloride (PH) forms a mixed-ligand complex with niobium under similar conditions which could be completely extracted into benzene³. However, MTM offers the advantage of higher selectivity in trichloroethylene which has not been attained with PH.

The formation and the extraction of the ternary complex was investigated with hydrochloric, sulphuric and phosphoric acids. Maximum intensity was achieved in 2–4 M HCl which was not possible in sulphuric acid and there was no colouration in phosphoric acid medium.

A number of organic solvents such as trichloroethylene, benzene, toluene, chloroform, chlorobenzene, ethyl acetate, butyl acetate and diethyl ether were used to extract the mixed ligand complex. It was observed that trichloroethylene (% *E*=100) and benzene (% *E*=100) were most suitable solvents as the extract exhibited maximum sensitivity, selectivity, stability and less interference from other associated ions. However, due to toxicity of benzene, trichloroethylene was chosen as the solvent.

It was observed that maximum absorbance was achieved in 1.5–3.5 ml of 20% ammonium thiocyanate and 3–6 ml of 0.5% MTM, for a solution containing upto 35 μg of niobium(v). Hence 2 ml of 20% thiocyanate and 4 ml of 0.5% MTM

solution were recommended. Constant absorbance values were obtained immediately after the extraction and remained stable for 24 h. The trichloroethylene extract of the ternary complex showed maximum absorbance at 400 nm where the reagent blank absorbed negligibly.

Beer's law was obeyed in the range 0.2–3.5 μg ml⁻¹ of niobium (v). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values were respectively $2.64 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0035 \text{ μg cm}^{-2}$ Nb at 400 nm. For 10 parallel determinations of 2 μg ml⁻¹ of Nb, the relative error and standard deviation were found to be 0.5% and 0.003 respectively.

The composition of the niobium complex with thiocyanate and MTM was studied spectrophotometrically by Job's method of continuous variation and equilibrium-shift method. The results indicated that the molar ratio of niobium to thiocyanate and niobium to MTM were 1:2 and 1:1 respectively.

The extent of interference of other metal ions usually associated with niobium and common anions was determined by measuring the absorbance of a solution containing 2 μg ml⁻¹ of niobium and various amounts of foreign ions. The following amounts of foreign ions (μg ml⁻¹) have been found to give less than 2% error: Mn^{II} (2500), Ni^{II} (150), La^{III} (100), Th^{IV} (100), Th^V (100), UO₂^{II} (100), Cr^{III} (100), Cu^{II} (50), Co^{II} (50), Zr^{IV} (10), W^{VI} (10), V^v (10), fluoride (1000), chloride (5000), bromide (2000), iodide (25), nitrate (100), sulphate (1000), phosphate (500), acetate (1000), oxalate (1000) and EDTA (5000). A 100-fold excess of Fe^{III} has been tolerated in the presence of 2 ml of 10% ascorbic acid as a masking agent.

The proposed method was applied to the determination of niobium in two standard mineral samples IGS-33 and IGS-34 obtained from Atomic Minerals Division, Bangalore. The sample (~0.2 g) was fused with potassium pyrosulphate (4 g). The cooled melt was dissolved in 10% tartaric acid (20 ml) and the solution made upto 100 ml with water. To an aliquot of the solution was added 2 ml of 10% ascorbic acid to mask iron(III) and the niobium content was determined following the above procedure. The results of the investigation on IGS-33 and IGS-34 show the values for niobium as 47.75% and 18.80% respectively which are in good agreement with the values 47.93% and 18.88% (certified by the Institute of Geological Sciences).

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Experimental

A Beckman DB spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. A stock solution of niobium(v) was prepared by fusing niobium pentoxide (Specpure) with potassium pyrosulphate (1:30). The fused melt was dissolved in 10% tartaric acid solution and made upto 250 ml. The stock solution was further diluted with 10% tartaric acid solution to get a working solution of $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. An aqueous solution of 0.5% MTM was prepared and stored in a refrigerator. A 20% aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate was freshly prepared. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade unless otherwise mentioned.

To an aliquot of the stock solution containing upto $35 \mu\text{g}$ of Nb^{V} was added 10 M HCl (3 ml), 0.5% MTM (4 ml) and trichloroethylene (6 ml). The mixture was equilibrated for 2 min and the phases were allowed to separate for 5 min. The organic phase was separated and the aqueous phase was once again equilibrated with trichloroethylene (3 ml). The two organic phases were

mixed, dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), made upto 10 ml with trichloroethylene and its absorbance was measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank.

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